

Virtual Reality and the inevitable mass unemployment in the movies industry

Abstract

VR in movies is the process of producing images and videos using only computer animations with technology without using actors who play the part.

Body

In the next few decades, almost all the movies in the world (roughly 95%-98% of them) will be made using VR thus cutting off actors and directors from the movies industry. Since using computer animation is far cheaper and takes far less budget to produce, producers will tend to use this technology than employing actors or directors who will inevitably remain without employment.

Movies in VR will be produced far better and more realistic than current VR thus making them almost seem like Real Reality (using actors) thus pushing the movies industry into adopting this new technology instead of using real actors (who have a high cost of employment).

Conclusion

VR will make it possible to produce movies with high quality and far cheaper than Real Reality (using actors). The consequences of this new approach in the movies industry will make the real/human actors obsolete. Another consequence of mass unemployment in the movies industry as a result of “automation” and computers that will force governments to implement Universal Basic Income.

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Tirana, Albania
10/19/2021